

Kinetics of Borosilicate Glass. Aqueous Phase Interaction

N. K. MITRA*, S. R. VASISTHA, A. C. DAS and A. BASUMAJUMDAR

Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

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Kinetics of aqueous phase interaction of borosilicate glasses of a particle size fraction, (-60+80) mesh B. S. S., were studied at 30, 50, and 98° by estimating SiO₂, B₂O₃, CaO, BaO, MgO, Na₂O and K₂O leached out under isothermal conditions. The rate of reaction was found to be diffusion-controlled although the magnitude of migration of different constituents varied due to intensity of interaction, diffusion barrier and their mutual interactions.

THE decomposition of glass is a highly complex reaction involving the penetration of the aqueous phase into the glass structure. Generally, the study of the diffusible ions from the glass structure is carried out to assess the suitability of glass for commercial applications. Lyle¹ derived an expression relating time and temperature with alkali extracted considering diffusion as rate controlling process. Elmer and Nodberg² carried out experiments on the solubility of silica gel in nitric acid medium. Bartholomew³ studied the kinetics of the attack of NaOH and KOH melts on various glasses and concluded that the mechanism of interaction is controlled by diffusion. Molchanova and Serebryakova⁴ studied the rate of interaction of alkali borosilicate glass with HCl, HF and KOH. Bershtein and Nikitin⁵ also studied the kinetics of mechanical destruction of glass in the presence of absorbed moisture.

In the present investigation the kinetics of dissolution of low melting alkali borosilicate glass in aqueous phase have been studied as the commercial application of borosilicate glass depends primarily on the durability in contact with water.

Experimental

Na₂O.B₂O₃.SiO₂ and K₂O.B₂O₃.SiO₂ systems of glasses were taken and a fixed proportion of Na₂O and K₂O was substituted by MgO, CaO and BaO respectively. Twelve glass samples were prepared out of which six contained Na₂O and the rest K₂O. Boric acid, borax, sodium carbonate, potassium carbonate, magnesium carbonate, calcium carbonate, barium carbonate were all of AnalaR grade and purified glass sand from Allahabad were selected for the preparation of glasses. The raw

materials were accurately weighed as per the batch composition, precalcined and the glasses were prepared in a gas-fired furnace at 1400°. Double-melting technique was adopted in all cases to ensure complete glass formation. The perfect glassy nature of all the glasses were further ascertained by X-ray analysis. A typical X-ray analysis figure of glass bearing no. G₁ is shown in Fig. 1. The prepared glasses were ground carefully, sieved to (-60+80) mesh B. S. S. and kept in airtight bottles. All the glasses were analysed for SiO₂, B₂O₃, CaO, BaO, MgO, Na₂O and K₂O by standard chemical methods^{6,7}. The kinetics study was carried out with the above glass powder at 30, 50 and 98°. 1.0 g of glass was used in each experiment and the constituents leached out in the aqueous phase in the isothermal condition were characterised as a function of time. The leaching operations were conducted upto 6 h except at 30° where it was conducted for 24 h. It may be mentioned that leaching operation at 50 and 98° was not conducted upto equilibrium as in the case of 30°. The isothermal condition was maintained by immersing the flasks containing the glass powder and the leaching agent in a constant temperature water-bath.

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of melted glasses were determined (Table 1).

Since the nature of time vs corrosion curves was more or less similar, curves for a typical glass are presented in Fig. 2. From the nature of rate curves it appears that the mechanisms of migration of the different constituents of the glasses in aqueous phase did not differ although the magnitudes were different depending on the intensity of interaction,

Fig. 1. X-Ray photograph of glass sample no. G₁.

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL COMPOSITIONS OF MELTED GLASSES

Glass sample no	Chemical compositions (mole percent)						
	SiO ₂	B ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	MgO	CaO	BaO
G ₁	70.52	19.48	9.85	—	—	—	—
G ₂	70.38	13.75	15.75	—	—	—	—
G ₃	70.41	9.85	19.63	—	—	—	—
G ₄	70.30	13.80	9.84	—	6.02	—	—
G ₅	70.28	13.78	9.83	—	—	6.05	—
G ₆	70.38	13.75	9.85	—	—	—	5.95
G ₇	70.28	13.68	—	9.85	—	—	—
G ₈	70.26	13.85	—	15.80	—	—	—
G ₉	70.25	9.90	—	19.70	—	—	—
G ₁₀	70.22	13.82	—	9.80	6.02	—	—
G ₁₁	70.20	13.85	—	9.82	—	6.05	—
G ₁₂	70.25	13.80	—	9.80	—	—	6.00

Fig. 2

diffusion barrier and mutual interaction of the constituents.

The leaching of the borosilicate glasses in the present investigation is a time-dependent process. The reaction rate initially increased and then decreased upto the equilibrium although curves were not drawn upto equilibrium. All the glasses in presence of distilled water as leaching agent showed a gradual decrease of rate of corrosion with time. Straight line relationships were obtained in all cases which indicates that the rate of decomposition of glass is controlled by equation (1),

$$Q^a = K T \quad (1)$$

where, Q is the amount of material extracted from the glass in time T , and a and K are constants. Taking logarithms of both sides of equation (1), as

suggested by Lyle¹, the following straight line relation with slope $1/a$ is obtained,

$$\log Q = \frac{1}{a} \log K + \frac{1}{a} \log T \quad (2)$$

Bacon and Burch⁸ measured the attack of water on some commercial bottle glasses. Using these results, Lyle¹ calculated the values of a of equation (2) and found to be in the range 0.9–2.0. In the present investigation, log of corrosion against log of time was plotted for all the individual constituents of the glasses for their leaching in distilled water operated at 98°. Because of similar nature, some of them are shown in Fig. 3. The values of a as calculated from the graphs are given in Table 2. From Table 2, it appears that the values of a for SiO₂ varied from 1.1 to 1.87 with the exception of the

Fig. 3

glass sample no. G₂, where the rate of extraction was extremely slow compared to the other glasses. Similar was the trend for other constituents with some exception. Thus in most cases, the value was within 2.0. This clearly indicates that the rate of

migration of all the constituents followed the same course.

TABLE 2—CALCULATED VALUES OF a FOR EACH CONSTITUENT FROM RATE CURVES DURING LEACHING WITH DISTILLED WATER AT 98°

Glass sample no.	SiO ₂	B ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O+K ₂ O	MgO+CaO+BaO
G ₁	1.25	1.77	1.70	—
G ₂	5.33	6.25	3.50	—
G ₃	1.62	3.50	1.94	—
G ₄	1.72	1.96	4.16	—
G ₅	1.25	2.00	2.34	1.90
G ₆	1.25	1.50	2.22	1.25
G ₇	1.87	1.37	1.56	—
G ₈	1.66	1.66	0.97	—
G ₉	1.09	1.50	1.12	—
G ₁₀	1.40	1.66	1.62	—
G ₁₁	1.41	1.80	1.56	2.04
G ₁₂	1.32	1.77	1.35	3.10

Similar plots were made for total corrosion of glasses during leaching at 98, 50 and 30° respectively, some of which are furnished in Fig. 4. The values of a were calculated (Table 3). From Table 3, it appears that the values of a are an inverse function of temperature of leaching, which in other ways indicates that the rate of reaction was proportional to temperature.

Fig. 4

TABLE 3—CALCULATED VALUES OF a FOR TOTAL CORROSION OF GLASSES FROM THE RATE CURVES DURING LEACHING WITH WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (°C)

Glass sample no.	98°	50°	30°
G ₁	1.58	3.50	3.60
G ₂	3.70	5.37	5.90
G ₃	2.36	4.30	5.40
G ₄	1.80	3.80	4.16
G ₅	1.60	2.35	4.16
G ₆	1.37	3.33	4.68
G ₇	1.60	2.18	6.00
G ₈	1.60	3.57	5.50
G ₉	1.25	3.87	4.15
G ₁₀	1.40	3.02	4.01
G ₁₁	1.60	2.60	5.71
G ₁₂	1.60	2.70	4.77

From the rate curves it can be said that the rate of extraction (total corrosion) was more with potash glasses than that of the corresponding soda glasses at 98° and the difference decreased with the decrease in temperature of leaching. From the kinetics study, it appears that the rate of corrosion of borosilicate glasses increased with substitution of alkaline earth oxides for alkali oxide in both soda and potash glasses; although the effect of substitution in potash glasses was not prominent at 98°. In soda glasses, the influence of individual constituents, e.g. MgO, CaO and BaO, was not very much significant in the kinetic study.

Conclusion: (i) From the nature of time-corrosion curves it appears that the mechanism of migration of different constituents from the glass structure did not differ although the magnitudes were different depending on the intensity of interactions, diffusion barrier and their mutual interactions. (ii) All the glasses showed a decrease in rate of corrosion and straight line relationship indicated the fact that the reaction was diffusion-controlled as was found by Lyle¹.

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